

1 **Evaluation of human plasma sample preparation protocols for untargeted metabolic profiles**
2 **analyzed by UHPLC-ESI-TOF-MS**

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9 **Abstract**

10 Eight human plasma preparation protocols were evaluated for their suitability for metabolomic studies by
11 ultra-high performance liquid chromatography coupled to electrospray ionization time-of-flight mass
12 spectrometer (UHPLC-ESI-TOF-MS): organic solvent protein precipitation (PPT) with either methanol or
13 acetonitrile in 2:1 and 3:1 (v:v) organic solvent:plasma ratios, solid phase extraction (SPE) using C18 or
14 Hybrid SPE cartridges, a combination of PPT and SPE C18 cartridges and microextraction by packed
15 sorbent. A design of the study in which the order of injection of the samples was not randomized is
16 presented. The analyses were carried out in a BEH C18 column (1.7 μm , 2.1 x 100 mm) using a linear
17 gradient from 100 % water to 100% methanol, both with 0.1 % formic acid, in 21 min. The most
18 reproducible protocol considering both univariate and multivariate results was PPT with acetonitrile in a
19 2:1 (v:v) organic solvent:plasma ratio, offering a mean coefficient of variation of the area of all the detected
20 features of 0.15 and one of the lowest Euclidean distances. On the other hand, the highest number of
21 extracted features was achieved using methanol in a 2:1 (v:v) ratio as PPT solvent, closely followed by the
22 same protocol with acetonitrile in a 2:1 (v:v) proportion, which only offers 1.2 % less repeatable features.
23 In terms of concentration of remaining protein, protocols based on PPT with ACN provided cleaner extracts
24 than protocols based on PPT with methanol. Finally, pairwise comparison showed that the use of PPT and
25 SPE based protocols, offers a different coverage of the metabolome.

26 Keywords: Metabolomics, plasma, sample treatment, reproducibility, Liquid chromatography-mass
27 spectrometry, Hybrid SPE.

28 1. Introduction

29 Metabolomics consists of the untargeted analysis of low molecular weight metabolites (< 1 kDa) in
30 biological samples [1-4]. The principal aim of this omic science is to provide an insight into the metabolic
31 status of complex living systems. Comparison of the metabolic profiles from different phenotypes can be
32 used to identify specific metabolic changes leading to the understanding of physiology, toxicology and
33 disease progression [5, 6].

34 The more widespread analytical platforms in metabolomics are nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy
35 (NMR) and mass spectrometry (MS) coupled to liquid chromatography (LC) or gas chromatography (GC)
36 [7]. Although NMR is more robust, repeatable and needs a simpler sample treatment, which is ideal for
37 high throughput analysis, this technique has an important drawback that is overcome by MS, its low
38 sensitivity. Historically most metabolomic studies were carried out using GC coupled to mass spectrometry,
39 but its limitations related to the molecular weight and type of metabolites that can be analyzed and the
40 extensive preparation required led to the emergence of liquid chromatography coupled to mass
41 spectrometry (LC-MS) as a metabolite profiling tool. When MS is coupled to ultra-high performance liquid
42 chromatography (UHPLC), it is able to analyze simultaneously thousands of metabolites requiring a small
43 sample volume for analysis. Nonetheless, MS does not provide as much structural information as NMR,
44 being more difficult to accomplish the identification of biomarkers. As the aforementioned techniques have
45 different strengths and drawbacks, the ideal case would be to analyze the same sample set by a combination
46 of them [7, 8].

47 In all fields of analytical chemistry it is vital to use a repeatable sample preparation protocol in order to
48 minimize the differences between samples due to the analytical process. This is especially important when
49 human samples are analyzed because the influence of diet, environmental effects as well as genetic-related
50 factors causes high interindividual variability itself. In a metabolomic study two different approaches can
51 be used for the comparison of different sample treatment protocols, univariate and multivariate analysis.
52 Using a traditional statistic approach the median and mean coefficient of variation (CV) of the intensities
53 of all detected features (pairs mass-to-charge ratio (m/z)-retention time (RT)) can be calculated among the

54 replicates of each of the different protocols. It is also possible to know the percentage of features that has a
55 CV value lower than a certain value among the replicates, for example 0.3, which is considered the
56 maximum acceptable value for the total error for targeted LC-MS analysis [9], and the percentage of
57 features present in all (% N all) or in a certain number of replicates. The comparison of these values between
58 protocols gives an overview of the differences in repeatability. However, it is important to bear in mind that
59 metabolomic data sets are complex matrices composed by thousands of features that should be also
60 analyzed using a multivariate approach to combine multiple features and enhance the statistical comparison
61 of methods. Principal component analysis (PCA) is the most suitable analysis for this purpose. One way of
62 analyzing the repeatability in PCA is calculating the intrareplicate distance within the model, Euclidean
63 distance (ED), value that gives a comparison of relative repeatability among the replicates.

64 As in metabolomics the general aim is to study as many metabolites as possible, the best sample preparation
65 would be the one in which the sample is modified as little as possible (for example a simple dilution is the
66 usual protocol for urine metabolomic studies [10]). Previous works have reported the study of sample
67 treatment of matrices such as liver [11, 12], plasma [13-18], cells or microbes [19-24], feces [25] by
68 different analytical techniques. In the case of plasma samples direct injection is not possible without the
69 rapid degradation of the columns and loss of sensitivity caused by the gradual build-up of non-volatile
70 compounds in the cone of the ionization source. For these reasons and due to the important ion suppression
71 caused by endogenous compounds in LC-MS, it is crucial to apply a clean-up step before the analysis. This
72 is usually achieved by protein precipitation (PPT) using organic solvents, being the most employed
73 methanol (MeOH) or acetonitrile (ACN). An alternative approach that does not involve necessarily PPT
74 and thus allows only the study of non strongly protein-bound metabolites is solid phase extraction (SPE).
75 A combination of organic solvent precipitation of proteins and SPE (SPE + PPT) can be used with the aim
76 of releasing metabolites bound to proteins and prolonging column life. These SPE approaches remove
77 substances that are prone to being strongly retained on the column if the same stationary phase is used.
78 Taking into account that one of the major challenges in metabolomics is the analysis of a great number of
79 plasma samples, the removal of these substances could be very helpful in order to keep the ionization source
80 clean and lengthen the column life. However, to our knowledge, SPE has only been applied in one

81 metabolomic study of plasma samples analyzed by LC-MS [17]. Finally another clean-up option is offered
82 by phospholipids removal cartridges such as Hybrid SPE. The packed-bed filter/frit assembly of these
83 cartridges acts as a depth filter for the concurrent physical removal of precipitated proteins and chemical
84 removal of phospholipids while small molecules pass through unretained, giving as a result a cleaner sample
85 in which ion suppression caused by phospholipids is eliminated [26]. Depending on the specific aim of each
86 study different sample preparation protocols should be considered.

87 In this study eight human plasma preparation protocols were evaluated for their suitability for UHPLC–
88 electrospray ionization (ESI) time-of-flight (TOF) MS based untargeted metabolomics: four of them based
89 on organic solvent protein precipitation with either ACN or MeOH in 2:1 and 3:1 (v:v) organic
90 solvent:plasma proportions, two approaches in which SPE C18 cartridges were used, with and without
91 previous protein precipitation step, Hybrid SPE cartridges and microextraction by packed sorbent (MEPS).
92 To our knowledge this is the first time that the effectiveness and repeatability of Hybrid SPE and MEPS
93 are evaluated in human plasma metabolomics. Other plasma sample preparation protocols, as lowering pH
94 with acid or protein denaturation using heat, were discarded from the beginning because according to Want
95 et al [15] the number of extracted features obtained with these protocols is considerably low. The aim of
96 this work was, therefore, to study these different human plasma preparation protocols by means of
97 univariate and multivariate analyses in order to select a reliable and repeatable sample preparation protocol
98 for the untargeted metabolic analysis of human plasma that offers the highest number of extracted features.
99 Other parameters as number of extracted features, reproducibility of a series of selected features and the
100 amount of protein remaining in each reconstituted plasma extract were also studied.

101 2. Materials and Methods

102 2.1 Reagents and materials

103 Solvents for LC-MS and sample preparation (MeOH and ACN) were OPTIMA® LC-MS grade and were
104 obtained from Fisher Scientific (Los Angeles, CA, USA). Formic acid (FA) and sodium formate, both LC-
105 MS grade, leucine enkephalin (HPLC grade), bovine serum albumin solution from (BSA) and Bradford
106 reagent were from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA). Purified water from a Millipore (Milford, MA,

107 USA) Milli-Q Element A10 water system was used along the study. For UHPLC-ESI-TOF-MS analysis,
108 96-well plates were from Waters (Milford, MA, USA); well plate cap mats were purchased from VWR
109 International (Leicestershire, UK); Hybrid SPE precipitation cartridges were purchased from Sigma-
110 Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA) and Strata-X SPE polymeric cartridges were from Phenomenex (Torrance,
111 CA, USA). For carrying out MEPS extraction an eVol® XR hand-held automated analytical syringe
112 coupled to a 500 µL MEPS syringe that contains a MEPS C18 cartridge, all purchased from SGE Analytical
113 Science (Victoria, Australia), was used.

114 2.2 Plasma samples

115 Blood samples from ten healthy volunteers were collected into EDTA tubes. Written informed consent was
116 obtained from all the volunteers. Plasma samples were prepared by centrifugation in an Eppendorf 5804 R
117 centrifuge (Hamburg, Germany) at 1200 g at 4 °C for 10 min. Pooled samples were prepared mixing equal
118 amounts of the 10 plasma samples into one vessel. This plasma pool was divided in 10 mL fractions that
119 were used to evaluate the different sample preparation protocols. All the samples were stored at -20 °C until
120 the analysis.

121 2.3 Plasma sample preparation

122 Frozen plasma was thawed on ice. Eight sample preparation protocols were compared (Fig 1), each using
123 6 preparation replicates and 3 instrumental replicates. All the samples extracts at the end of the treatment
124 contained the same proportion plasma:reconstitution solvent (MeOH:H₂O 50:50 v:v).

125 2.3.1 Organic solvent PPT

126 This type of sample preparation consisted of a protein precipitation with either cold MeOH or ACN. The
127 starting volume of plasma was 250 µL. Two different ratios of organic solvent:plasma were tested, 2:1 and
128 3:1 (v:v). After brief vortexing, plasma samples were centrifuged at 13000 g for 5 min. 600 µL and 800
129 µL of the supernatant were taken for 2:1 and 3:1 (v:v) ratios, respectively, and they were dried under a
130 stream of N₂ at 40 °C in a Zymark Turbovap evaporator (Barcelona, Spain). Finally, the dried extracts were
131 reconstituted in 200 µL of MeOH:H₂O 50:50 (v:v).

132 2.3.2 Solid phase extraction procedure

133 Two SPE approaches were studied, one included a protein precipitation step prior to the extraction and the
134 other a simple dilution of the plasma sample with H₂O. The protein precipitation was carried out with
135 MeOH in a ratio 3:1 (v:v) MeOH:plasma, as it was detailed in the previous section, but instead of
136 evaporating the supernatant to dryness, when the volume was less than 200 µL, 800 µL of H₂O were added.
137 In the case of the dilution with H₂O, 800 µL of H₂O were added to 200 µL of plasma. SPE cartridges were
138 previously activated with 1 mL of MeOH and then further conditioned with 1 mL of H₂O. Diluted samples
139 were loaded into the cartridge and cleaned with 1 mL of H₂O. Subsequently, 1 mL of MeOH was used as
140 elution solvent. Finally, the eluate was dried under N₂ stream at 40 °C and reconstituted in 200 µL of
141 MeOH:H₂O 50:50 (v:v).

142 2.3.3 Microextraction by packed sorbent

143 First MEPS C18 cartridge was activated with 100 µL of MeOH and then further conditioned with 1 mL of
144 H₂O. Then 100 µL of plasma diluted with 400 µL of H₂O were loaded into the cartridge. After the cleaning
145 of the sample with 100 µL of H₂O, 500 µL of MeOH were used for elution. The guide provided by the
146 manufacturers (SGE Analytical Science, Victoria, Australia) was followed for this protocol. Finally, the
147 eluate was dried under N₂ stream at 40 °C and reconstituted in 100 µL of MeOH:H₂O 50:50 (v:v).

148 2.3.4 Hybrid SPE procedure

149 The protocol performed was the one recommended by the manufacturers (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO,
150 USA). Firstly a protein precipitation step was carried out by the addition of 750 µL of cold 1 % FA in ACN
151 to 250 µL of plasma. After a short vortexing the mixture was centrifuged at 1600 g for 3 min. Then 800 µL
152 of the supernatant were loaded into the Hybrid SPE cartridge and vacuum was applied. At this point the
153 eluate is ready for immediate LC-MS/MS analysis, but in order to make this method comparable with the
154 rest of the protocols, it was dried under N₂ stream at 40 °C and reconstituted in 200 µL of MeOH:H₂O 50:50
155 (v:v).

156 2.4 UHPLC-ESI-TOF-MS analysis

157 Analysis was performed using an Acquity UPLC System coupled to a electrospray ionization quadrupole-
158 time-of-flight (Q-TOF) Synapt-G2 mass spectrometer (UHPLC-ESI-Q-TOF-MS) (Waters, Milford, MA,
159 USA), operated in positive electrospray ionization mode (ESI +). Chromatography was carried out at 40 °C
160 on a Waters Acquity BEH C18 column (1.7 μm, 2.1 x 100 mm) with the following solvent system: A = 0.1
161 % FA in H₂O and B = 0.1 % FA in MeOH. A linear gradient was used at a flow rate of 0.5 mL/min from
162 100 % A to 100 % B in 21 min. Then 100 % B was hold for 2 min, after this time initial conditions were
163 reached, and finally, a 3 min re-equilibration step was included. The injection volume was 5 μL. ESI
164 conditions were source temperature 120 °C, desolvation temperature 450 °C, cone gas flow 10 L/h,
165 desolvation gas flow 900 L/h, capillary voltage 0.7 kV and cone voltage 30 V. TOF detector worked in
166 Resolution mode (approximately 2000 FWHM) and all mass spectral data were acquired in centroid mode
167 by scanning a m/z range of 50-1200 with a scan time of 0.1 s and an interscan delay time of 0.02 s. The
168 quadrupole was not used in this study. Leucine enkephalin ([M+H]⁺ = 556.2771 m/z) (2 ng/μL in 0.1 % FA
169 in ACN:H₂O 50:50 v:v) was employed as a lock mass, infused straight into the MS at a flow rate of 10
170 μL/min. The instrument was calibrated before the analysis using a 0.5 mM sodium formate solution
171 (calibration error < 1 ppm). All UHPLC-ESI-TOF-MS operations were run under the control of MassLynx
172 4.1 (Waters, Milford, MA, USA) software.

173 2.5 Design of the analysis

174 A blank, consisted of MeOH:H₂O 50:50 (v:v) solution, was included at the beginning and at the end of the
175 run in order to test any possible contamination or carryover effect. A quality control sample (QC), prepared
176 by combining equal aliquots of the replicates from each method, was injected regularly every 8 injections
177 throughout the run to monitor the sensitivity and the stability of the UHPLC-ESI-TOF-MS platform. This
178 QC sample was also used to condition the system at the beginning of the analysis (QCcond). It was observed
179 in a previous test that at least 15 injections of a sample containing the studied matrix were necessary to
180 stabilize the system and that even after the analysis of a few number of plasma samples the sensitivity fell
181 (data not shown). For this reason and bearing in mind the purpose of the study (evaluating the repeatability
182 of each of the sample preparation protocols), the order of injection of the samples was not randomized to
183 minimize the effect of the instrumental drift arising from column degradation or contamination of the MS

184 source on the evaluation of repeatability within each protocol. In Table 1 the analysis order is shown. The
185 preparation replicates of each protocol were injected one after the other. Instrumental replicates of one of
186 the preparation replicate were injected between them (Replicate 1_1, 1_2 and 1_3). Although this way of
187 analyzing the samples is the most convenient to study the repeatability, it is not the optimum to set the
188 number of extracted features taking into consideration the drop of sensitivity throughout the run. This
189 problem was overcome analyzing in a different batch 3 replicates of each protocol randomly (data not
190 shown).

191 2.6 Data processing

192 The raw spectrometric data acquired were processed using XCMS software [27] (version 1.30.3) in order
193 to convert the three-dimensional LC-MS raw data (RT, m/z, intensity) into a table of time-aligned detected
194 features, with their RT, m/z and intensity in each sample. XCMS is written in R statistical programming
195 language and is freely available under an open-source license. The version of R used was 2.14.1. The
196 samples were grouped according to the different sample preparation protocols. Blanks and QC samples
197 were treated as separate groups. “CentWave” algorithm [28] was used for peak picking with a peak width
198 window of 3-20 s (peakwidth=c(3,20)) and a maximum tolerated m/z deviation in consecutive scans for a
199 peak of 15 ppm (ppm = 15). The m/z width for the grouping was set to 0.015 Da (mzwid = 0.015) and the
200 bandwidth parameter chosen was 5 s (bw = 5) for the first grouping and then determined from the time
201 deviation profile after retention time correction. These values are the commonly used in UHPLC coupled
202 to a high resolution mass spectrometer and studying the raw data and the results obtained it was decided
203 that they were appropriate for the analysis carried out. The rest of the parameters were set to the default
204 values. Finally the missed peaks during the peak picking algorithm were integrated automatically with the
205 “fillPeak” function. This step is essential for reducing the observed CV values, as many zero values are
206 replaced with real peak intensities. In order to avoid LC-MS artifacts (those peaks that do not represent
207 molecular ions of metabolites such as isotopes, common adducts and fragments, multiple charge states,
208 etc), R-package CAMERA was used to filter the detected peaks. The generated peak marker tables
209 (comprising pairs m/z-RT and their corresponding intensity values for each sample) were exported into
210 Microsoft Office Excel 2007 (Redmond, WA, USA) for univariate analysis and into SIMCA-P+ 11.5

211 (Umetrics, Umea, Sweden) for multivariate analysis. Data out of the interval 0.5-21 min, that is, up to the
212 elution peak and from the point at which column washing step of the analysis started, were discarded.

213 2.7 Evaluation of method repeatability

214 In order to obtain the most in-depth information of sample preparation repeatability, data were analyzed
215 using two different approaches, univariate and multivariate statistics. Furthermore, other parameters
216 calculated directly from the resulting table from XCMS, as the total number of features and the coefficient
217 of variation of the area of some selected features for each protocol, can be used to study the repeatability
218 of each protocol.

219 2.7.1 Multivariate statistics

220 Principal components analysis (PCA) was performed on all data after logarithmic transformation
221 ($10\log(\text{peak area})$) and mean centering. Scores plots were examined to assess the degree of similarity
222 between the different protocols and to identify outliers or trends in data. The ED within the PCA data was
223 calculated for the intrareplicate distance within the model [29] for each protocol taking into account the
224 first three principal components. These ED values give a comparison of relative repeatability among the
225 replicates, which can be difficult to observe in the obtained 3D PCA score. The lowest this value is the
226 better repeatability it indicates.

227 2.7.2 Univariate statistics

228 Univariate statistics were used to compare the CV distribution of feature intensity among the replicates for
229 each protocol. Another way of comparing the CV distribution is calculating the percentage (or number) of
230 features which have a CV lower than a certain value. In this work the number of features with a CV value
231 lower than 0.15, 0.20 and 0.30 were calculated. These two first values are the CV values considered to
232 represent an acceptable degree of repeatability according to the International Conference on Harmonisation
233 (ICH) [30] for bioanalytical methods for targeted analysis in any concentration (0.15), except for the one
234 corresponding to the limit of quantitation (0.20) and the latter (0.30) the acceptable CV value in biomarkers
235 analysis [17].

236 2.8 Other parameters

237 In order to select the most suitable sample preparation protocol for metabolic profiling there are some other
238 parameters that also should be considered. These are: the total number of features obtained and the area
239 deviation of some selected features for each protocol. As the behavior of each detected feature depends on
240 its own chemical structure and the RT at which it elutes from the chromatographic column, no internal
241 labeled standards are commonly used in metabolomics. For this reason the area deviation offered by each
242 protocol was assessed by studying six features with different RTs and m/z present in all the replicates of all
243 the protocols.

244 2.9 Protein concentration estimation

245 The Bradford assay was employed to estimate the amount of protein remaining in three replicates of each
246 reconstituted plasma preparation protocol. Samples were first diluted 1:2 (v:v) with distilled H₂O and then
247 mixed with Bradford reagent in a ratio of 1:20 (v:v) sample:Bradford reagent. A calibration curve was
248 generated using known concentrations (from 0.78 to 100 mg/L) of a standard protein (BSA).

249 3 Results

250 The 8 sample preparation protocols (each performed on 6 preparation replicates and 3 instrumental
251 replicates) were compared resulting in a set of 90 injections, 64 plasma samples plus 24 QC samples (QC
252 + QC conditioning) and 2 blanks. Different criteria were used to evaluate the protocols: repeatability by
253 multivariate and univariate analyses, number of extracted features, repeatability of a series of selected
254 features and the amount of protein remaining in each reconstituted plasma extract.

255 3.1 Feature distribution

256 The base peak intensity (BPI) chromatograms obtained with all the sample preparation protocols show the
257 feature distribution along chromatographic time (Fig 2). In general, until the minute 16 all of them, except
258 Hybrid SPE and MEPS had similar profiles with different intensities and number of visible features,
259 especially higher for ACN 2:1 and MeOH 2:1. From this minute on, in the cases of Hybrid SPE, MEPS,

260 direct SPE and SPE + PPT, fewer chromatographic peaks were detected comparing with the rest of
261 protocols, and again ACN 2:1 and MeOH 2:1 provided the highest peak intensities and number of features.
262 Taking into account that the last minutes correspond to the lipophilic region we could conclude that solvent
263 precipitation extracts had more lipophilic material than other protocols and that the removal of a great part
264 of this kind of compounds was achieved when any cartridge was used for sample preparation.

265 3.2 Evaluation of method repeatability using multivariate statistics

266 The repeatability of the chromatographic method used was assessed in the PCA. A clear tendency of the
267 QCs is observed as the instrument sensitivity falls (44 % of signal drop from the first QC to the last one,
268 data not shown). The explained variation (R^2X) was 70.5, 79.9 and 86.7 for the first, second and third
269 principal components, respectively, and the predicted variation (Q^2X) for these components was 70.2, 79.5
270 and 86.1. When the model was built without including the QCs samples in the data processing step (Fig 3),
271 in order to avoid their effect in the PCA, a high increase in R^2X and Q^2X parameter was observed for the
272 first three components (91.6, 96.0 and 97.9 and 88.5, 92.6 and 95.8, respectively). All the protocols were
273 well separated from each other and the results agreed with the differences observed in the BPI
274 chromatograms. This can be observed in the distribution of the sample treatment protocols along the first
275 principal component.

276 In order to give a number to the relative repeatability of the protocols shown by PCA scores plot, the ED
277 values generated from the first three components were calculated. In Fig 4, the ED values represent the
278 mean of the distances among the replicates of a particular protocol.

279 ACN 2:1 protocol yielded the lowest mean ED value. When this value was statistically compared (95 %
280 confidence level) with the ED values of the rest of sample preparation protocols significant differences
281 were obtained in all cases, except for SPE + PPT .

282 3.3 Evaluation of method repeatability using univariate statistics

283 Box plots were used to visualize the distribution of feature intensity CV values among the replicates (Fig
284 5). Each box shows the degree of dispersion of CV values of features for one condition by displaying the

285 25th percentile (bottom of the box), the median, the mean and the 75th percentile (top of the box). According
286 to this plot, the protocols based on solvent precipitation with ACN in a 2:1 organic solvent:plasma ratio,
287 showing a median and mean CV of 0.12 and 0.15, respectively, was the most repeatable protocol. An
288 analysis of variance confirmed that the observed differences between protocols were significant.

289 Another way of visualizing the distribution of feature intensity CV values is calculating the number of
290 extracted features for each method with an intensity CV lower than 0.15, 0.20 and 0.30. These data are
291 shown in Fig 6. In terms of number of consistently detected features, again ACN 2:1 protocol seemed to be
292 the most repeatable protocol, having the 93 % of the features a CV below 0.30. It is important to bear in
293 mind that the values of the total number of features indicated in this section is not real because it is affected
294 by the fall of sensitivity during the analysis.

295 3.4 Number of extracted features

296 The number of extracted features from XCMS for each protocol was also considered in the selection of
297 optimal conditions. As it was mentioned in section 2.5 this value was calculated injecting in a different
298 batch only 3 replicates from each protocol randomly, so that the drop of sensitivity along a long run does
299 not lead to an underestimation of the number of features of the samples analyzed at the end of the batch
300 (data not shown). The obtained order, in terms of number of extracted features, did not differ from the one
301 observed in the designed run. As Table 2 shows, the maximum number of detected features was achieved
302 with PPT with MeOH 2:1 as protocol closely followed by ACN 2:1. The best feature extraction efficiency
303 of MeOH in serum samples was reported by Want et al [15] and in plasma samples by Bruce et al [16]. A
304 high decrease in the number of extracted features was observed for Hybrid SPE, MEPS and direct SPE,
305 which makes sense taking into account that the former includes a mechanism for the removal of
306 phospholipids and in C18 cartridges based protocols without a previous protein precipitation step protein
307 bound compounds are not studied, while protocols including a protein precipitation step result in a drastic
308 alteration of the 3D structure of proteins that allows the release of metabolites bound to them.

309 The number of common repeatable features between methods was calculated. Pairwise comparisons of the
310 different plasma preparation protocols showing the number of common features and its percentage taking

311 as 100 % the total detected features in the protocol with less total detected features in each case are indicated
312 in Table 2. A high percentage of common features (> 76 %) can be seen for the different proportions of
313 organic solvent:plasma used, higher in the case of ACN (87 %). On the other hand, it is observed that using
314 solid phase extraction protocols it is possible to detect features that are not observed in PPT protocols,
315 meaning that both types of protocol are complementary.

316 3.5 Repeatability of selected metabolites

317 Analytical and sample preparation repeatability was further investigated using selected features. For this
318 purpose 6 features with different RTs and m/z present in all the replicates of all the protocols were chosen.
319 Table 3 lists these features and their measured m/z value, RTs, and intensity CV among the replicates for
320 each protocol.

321 All the protocols provided a mean CV value < 0.2, yielding the best results in terms of repeatability SPE +
322 PPT, offering a mean CV value of 0.12 among preparation replicates and 0.04 when only instrumental
323 replicates are taken into account.

324 3.6 Protein concentration

325 The concentration of residual protein was estimated for each plasma preparation protocol using Bradford
326 assay. According to the results obtained by Bruce et al [16] ACN offers a better protein removal efficiency
327 than MeOH in plasma samples. As it can be observed in Table 4, our results agree with these observations
328 being both protein precipitations protocols based on PPT with MeOH the ones that contained the largest
329 amount of residual protein. The efficiency of SPE cartridges in terms of protein removal has not been
330 reported before in any of the aforementioned studies, but attending to these results, the use of these
331 cartridges helps to get a cleaner extract compared with a simple PPT with MeOH, as it was expected. It is
332 worthwhile to remark that in the case of SPE + PPT protocol, MeOH was used as organic solvent for PPT
333 and, therefore, that maybe if ACN had been used as protein precipitation solvent this combination would
334 have got the lowest remaining protein concentration.

335 4 Discussion

336 Many reported approaches for plasma sample preparation have focused on a small subset of metabolites
337 [14, 16-18]. As our aim was to perform untargeted metabolic profiling of plasma samples encompassing a
338 wide range of chemical structures, it was also essential to study the repeatability of the different plasma
339 preparation protocols used for all the detected features, as it was reported by Want et al [15]. For this reason
340 efficiency and repeatability of the selected plasma preparation protocols were investigated using univariate
341 and multivariate analyses and other parameters, such as feature distribution, number of extracted features,
342 the repeatability of some selected features and the amount of protein remaining in the reconstituted samples,
343 were studied. All of these criteria should be taken into account for selecting a sample preparation protocol
344 for metabolic profiling studies.

345 To our knowledge only in one work the evaluation of the use of SPE cartridges in metabolomics has been
346 carried out [17], but authors did not study sample preparation repeatability. On the other hand, it is the first
347 time in which the efficiency of SPE + PPT, MEPS and Hybrid SPE in metabolomics is evaluated.

348 Before starting to analyze the different studied plasma preparation protocols it is worth pointing out that an
349 appropriate design of the study is essential to fulfill the desired aim. The applied LC-MS method entails a
350 drop of sensitivity along a single run (44 %) and this fact needs to be taken into consideration, otherwise
351 the results would not be reliable at all. The proposed design to solve this problem is to inject the samples,
352 instead of randomly, classified by protocols. In this way the highest drop of sensitivity within a protocol is
353 only of 7 % (calculated from the instrumental replicates) and the distance from the first replicate to the last
354 one is constant for all the protocols. Another point to bear in mind related to the drop of sensitivity is its
355 effect on the number of detected features parameter. To overcome this, a different analysis in which only 3
356 preparation replicates of each protocol are analyzed randomly is carried out.

357 After the evaluation of the different criteria applied, we found that PPT with ACN in a 2:1 (v/v) ratio with
358 plasma produced the best results for most of the parameters studied. This protocol offered one of the lowest
359 EDs between replicates in multivariate analysis, the lowest CV values in univariate analysis, good
360 repeatability of the selected features, and one of the lowest concentrations of remaining protein in the final
361 extract. Furthermore, although PPT with ACN in a 2:1 ratio with plasma offered 9.5 % fewer total detected

362 features than PPT with MeOH in a 2:1 ratio with plasma, the difference in terms of repeatable features
363 (CV<0.30) was only 1.2 %. The satisfactory results in terms of repeatability could be explained by the
364 combination of the simplicity of the sample preparation protocol itself (the same for all the PPT protocols)
365 and the high efficiency of ACN as a PPT agent (the HybridSPE protocol also included a PPT with ACN
366 step). The better results achieved by PPTwith ACN when compared with MeOHin terms of repeatability
367 could be explained by the fact that the extracts obtained with PPT using ACN as an organic solvent
368 exhibited lower ionization suppression than the ones obtained with MeOH [31]. On the other hand, in the
369 comparison of PPTwith ACN with the HybridSPE protocol it must be taken into account that the
370 HybridSPE protocol includes an additional step that could be the cause of the observed differences in
371 repeatability. The lower number of extracted features of the protocols that include retention mechanisms
372 was probably due, on the one hand, in the case of direct SPE and MEPS, to the fact that metabolites bound
373 to proteins are not released and, on the other hand, when HybridSPE cartridges were used, to the removal
374 of phospholipids. Finally, according to the Bradford assay, the extracts obtained using ACN as an agent for
375 PPTwere cleaner than the ones obtained with MeOH, which were the extracts that contained the highest
376 concentration of remaining proteins. This agrees with the results reported by Bruce et al. [16], and thus,
377 MeOH should not be an option when a long column life is desired.

378 Although MichopoulosAlthough Michopoulos et al [17] observed that SPE offered good repeatability, our
379 results do not totally agree when it is compared with PPT protocols. A reason for this difference could be
380 that they did not include in their work preparation replicates and that they only focused on a small subset
381 of metabolites. Another fact that differs from their study and ours is that all our protocols were carried out
382 manually and they used an automatized SPE station, which could significantly improve repeatability. Want
383 et al [15] set that ACN was the organic solvent which provided less repeatability in terms of univariate
384 analysis in serum samples. The reason for the difference between their results and ours cannot be easily
385 established, but could be because serum and plasma are similar, but different matrices. Another explanation
386 could be that they injected the sample preparation replicates randomly, and therefore, sample treatments
387 with replicates further from each other show a higher CV owing to the decay in sensitivity.

388 The MEPS and HybridSPE protocols did not result in the expected good repeatability, but maybe the
389 automatization of the processes and/or the optimization of the parameters that affect the extractions could
390 significantly improve the results.

391 In terms of complementarity it is important to mention that pairwise comparison showed that many of the
392 detected features in protocols that included solid phase extraction mechanism were not detected when only
393 PPT protocols were used. These findings mean that combining both types of protocols a higher coverage
394 of the metabolome could be obtained.

395 Finally, this work shows an approach to compare the results obtained from different sample preparation
396 protocols for untargeted metabolomics that takes into consideration many different parameters that affect
397 directly the results. This strategy could be applied to any other matrix and/or sample preparation protocols.

398 5 Conclusions

399 We have reported an appropriate design of a study for the evaluation of different human plasma sample
400 preparation protocols for use in a metabolomic study. After the evaluation of the eight plasma preparation
401 protocols studied (based on organic solvent precipitation or three different cartridges or a combination of
402 both), we can conclude that a simple PPT with ACN in a 2:1 (v/v) ratio with plasma is the protocol that
403 globally better satisfies all the requirements established: the best results in terms of univariate and
404 multivariate repeatability, a high number of extracted features, and good removal of proteins from the
405 sample, which is very relevant when a great number of samples is to be analyzed. On the other hand, the
406 use of PPT- and cartridge-based extraction protocols offers a different coverage of the metabolome.

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413 7 References

414 [1] Nicholson JK, Lindon JC, Holmes E (1999) 'Metabonomics': understanding the metabolic responses of
415 living systems to pathophysiological stimuli via multivariate statistical analysis of biological NMR
416 spectroscopic data. *Xenobiotica* 29:1181-1189

417 [2] Goodacre R, Vaidyanathan S, Dunn WB, Harrigan GG, Kell DB (2004) Metabolomics by numbers:
418 acquiring and understanding global metabolite data. *Trends Biotechnol* 22:245-252

419 [3] Fiehn O, Kopka J, Dormann P, Altmann T, Trethewey RN, Willmitzer L, (2000) Metabolite profiling
420 for plant functional genomics. *Nat Biotechnol* 18:1157-1161

421 [4] Van der Greef J, Stroobant P, Van der Heijden R (2004) The role of analytical sciences in medical
422 systems biology. *Curr Opin Chem Biol* 8:559-565

423 [5] Lindon JC, Nicholson JK, Holmes E (2007) *The Handbook of Metabonomics and Metabolomics*.
424 Elsevier, Amsterdam

425 [6] Griffiths WJ (2008) *Metabolomics, metabonomics and metabolite profiling*. The Royal Society of Chemistry,
426 Cambridge

427 [7] Lenz EM, Wilson ID (2007) Analytical strategies in metabolomics. *J Proteome Res* 6:443-458.

428 [8] Pan Z, Raftery D (2007) Comparing and combining NMR spectroscopy and mass spectrometry in
429 metabolomics. *Anal Bioanal Chem* 387:525-527

430 [9] Viswanathan CT, Bansal S, Booth B, DeStefano AJ, Rose MJ, Sailstad J, Shah VP, Skelly JP, Swann
431 PG, Weiner R (2007) Quantitative bioanalytical methods validation and implementation: Best practices for
432 chromatographic and ligand binding assays. *Pharm Res* 24:1962-1973

- 433 [10] Gika HG, Theodoridis GA, Wingate JE, Wilson ID (2007) Within-day reproducibility of an LC-MS-
434 based method for metabonomic analysis: application to human urine. *J Proteome Res* 6(8):3291-303
- 435 [11] Masson P, Alves AC, Ebbels TM, Nicholson JK, Want EJ (2010) Optimization and evaluation of
436 metabolite extraction protocols for untargeted metabolic profiling of liver samples by UPLC-MS. *Anal*
437 *Chem* 82(18):7779-7786
- 438 [12] Pan L, Qiu Y, Chen T, Lin J, Chi Y, Su M, Zhao A, Jia W (2010) An optimized procedure for
439 metabonomic analysis of rat liver tissue using gas chromatography/time-of-flight mass spectrometry. *J*
440 *Pharm Biomed* 52(4):589-596
- 441 [13] Jiye A, Trygg J, Gullberg J, Johansson AI, Jonsson P, Antti H, Marklund SL, Moritz T (2005) Extraction
442 and GC/MS analysis of the human blood plasma metabolome. *Anal Chem* 77:8086-8094
- 443 [14] Bruce SJ, Jonsson P, Antti H, Cioarec O, Trygg J, Marklund SL, Moritz T (2008) Evaluation of a
444 protocol for metabolic profiling studies on human blood plasma by combined UPLC-MS: from extraction
445 to data analysis. *Anal Biochem* 372:237-249
- 446 [15] Want EJ, O'Maille G, Smith CA, Brandon TR, Uritboonthai W, Qin C, Trauger SA, Siuzdak G. (2006)
447 Solvent-dependent metabolite distribution, clustering, and protein extraction for serum profiling with mass
448 spectrometry. *Anal Chem* 78:743-752
- 449 [16] Bruce SJ, Tavazzi I, Parisod V, Rezzi S, Kochhar S, Guy PA (2009) Investigation of human blood
450 plasma sample preparation for performing metabolomics using ultrahigh performance liquid
451 chromatography/mass spectrometry. *Anal Chem* 81:3285-3296
- 452 [17] Michopoulos F, Lai L, Gika HG, Theodoridis G, Wilson ID (2009) UPLC-MS-based analysis of
453 human plasma for metabolomics using solvent precipitation or solid phase extraction. *J Proteome Res*,
454 8:2114-2121

- 455 [18] Tulipani S, Llorach R, Urpi-Sarda M, Andres-Lacueva C (2013) Comparative analysis of sample
456 preparation methods to handle the complexity of the blood fluid metabolome: when less is more. *Anal*
457 *Chem* 85(1):341-348
- 458 [19] Marcinowska R, Trygg J, Wolf-Watz H, Mortiz T, Surowiec I (2011) Optimization of a sample
459 preparation method for the metabolomic analysis of clinically relevant bacteria. *J Microbiol Methods*
460 87(1):24-31
- 461 [20] Madla S, Miura D, Wariishi H (2012) Optimization of extraction method for GC-MS based
462 metabolomics for *filamentous fungi*. *J Microbial Biochem Technol* 4(1):5-9
- 463 [21] Sellick CA, Knight D, Croxford AS, Maqsood AR, Stephens GM, Goodacre R, Dickson AJ (2010)
464 Evaluation of extraction processes for intracellular metabolite profiling of mammalian cells: matching
465 extraction approaches to cell type and metabolite targets. *Metabolomics* 6(3):427-438
- 466 [22] Dettmer K, Nurnberger N, Kaspar H, Gruber MA, Almstetter MF, Oefner PJ (2011) Metabolite
467 extraction from adherently growing mammalian cells for metabolomics studies: optimization of harvesting
468 and extraction protocols. *Anal Bioanal Chem*, 399(3):1127-1139
- 469 [23] Neubauer S, Haberhauer-Troyer C, Klavins K, Russmayer H, Steiger MG, Gasser B, Sauer M,
470 Mattanovich D, Hann S, Koellensperger G (2012) U13C cell extract of *Pichia pastoris* - a powerful tool for
471 evaluation of sample preparation in metabolomics. *J Sep Sci* 35:3091-3105
- 472 [24] Kim S, Lee DY, Wohlgemuth G, Park HS, Fiehn, O, Kim H (2013) Evaluation and optimization of
473 metabolome sample preparation methods for *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. *Anal Chem* 85(4):2169-2176
- 474 [25] Wu J, An Y, Yao J, Wang Y, Tang H (2010) An optimised sample preparation method for NMR-based
475 faecal metabonomic analysis. *Analyst* 135:1023-1030

476 [26] Jiang H, Zhang Y, Ida M, LaFayette A, Fast DM (2011) Determination of carboplatin in human plasma
477 using HybridSPE-precipitation along with liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry. J
478 Chromatogr B 879(22):2162-2170

479 [27] Smith CA, Want EJ, O'Maille G, Abagyan R, Siuzdak G (2006) XCMS: processing mass spectrometry
480 data for metabolite profiling using nonlinear peak alignment, matching, and identification. Anal Chem
481 78:779-787

482 [28] Tautenhahn R, Böttcher C, Neumann, S (2008) Highly sensitive feature detection for high resolution
483 LC/MS. BMC Bioinformatics, 9:504-519

484 [29] Guy PA, Tavazzi I, Bruce SJ, Ramadan Z, Kochhar SJ (2008) Global metabolic profiling analysis on
485 human urine by UPLC-TOF-MS: Issues and method validation in nutritional metabolomics. J Chromatogr B
486 871:253-260

487 [30] ICH Expert Working Work. ICH Harmonised tripartite guideline, validation of analytical procedures:
488 Text and methodology Q2 (R1) (2005) Geneva

489 [31] Polson C, Sarkar P, Incledon B, Raguvaran V, Grant R (2003) Optimization of protein precipitation
490 based upon effectiveness of protein removal and ionization effect in liquid chromatography-tandem mass
491 spectrometry. J Chromatogr B 785:263-275

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Organic solvent protein precipitation

Solid phase extraction

Microextraction by packed solvent

HybridSPE

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Fig. 1 Sample treatment protocols evaluated. ACN acetonitrile, MeOH methanol

Table 1 Order of sample injection

Order of injection of the different protocols	Injection schedule within each protocol
15 QC conditioning	QC
MEPS	Replicate 1_1
SPE	Replicate 2
HybridSPE	Replicate 3
SPE + PPT	Replicate 1_2
MeOH 2:1	Replicate 4
ACN 2:1	Replicate 5
MeOH 3:1	Replicate 6
ACN 3:1	Replicate 1_3
	QC

ACN 2:1 acetonitrile in a 2:1 (v/v) ratio with plasma, *ACN 3:1* acetonitrile in a 3:1 (v/v) ratio with plasma, *MEPS* microextraction by packed sorbent, *MeOH 2:1* methanol in a 2:1 (v/v) ratio with plasma, *MeOH 3:1* methanol in a 3:1 (v/v) ratio with plasma, *PPT* protein precipitation, *QC* quality control, *SPE* solid-phase extraction

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Fig. 2 Raw base peak intensity ultra-high-performance liquid chromatography (UHPLC)–electrospray ionization–time-of-flight mass spectrometry chromatograms of a pooled plasma sample treated with the eight preparation protocols—ACN in a 2:1 (v/v) ratio with plasma (ACN 2:1), ACN in a 3:1 (v/v) ratio with plasma (ACN 3:1), MeOH in a 2:1 (v/v) ratio with plasma (MeOH 2:1), MeOH in a 3:1 (v/v) ratio with plasma (MeOH 3:1), HybridSPE, microextraction by packed sorbent (MEPS), solid phase extraction (SPE) and protein precipitation (PPT), and direct SPE—injected through a BEH C₁₈ HPLC column (2.1 mm×100 mm).

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Fig. 3 Three-dimensional principal component analysis scores plot for all the plasma preparation protocols after removal of liquid chromatography–mass spectrometry artifacts and quality control samples

Fig. 4 Calculated Euclidean distances (ED) (expressed as mean±confidence interval (95 % confidence level))

Fig. 5 Box plots comparing the distribution of feature intensity coefficients of variation (CV) among replicates for the different sample preparation protocols. For each box, the bottom corresponds to the 25th percentile, the middle band corresponds to the median (numerical value indicated), the diamond corresponds to the mean, and the top corresponds to the 75th percentile

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Fig. 6 Distribution of repeatable features for each protocol. The numbers above the columns express the percentage of features with a CV<0.30 of the total number of detected features

Table 2 Pairwise comparison showing the number of common features and the percentage, taking as 100 % the total detected features in the protocol, and the total detected features in each case

	ACN 2:1	ACN 3:1	HybridSPE	MeOH 2:1	MeOH 3:1	MEPS	SPE + PPT	SPE	Total
SPE	592 (67)	533 (60)	494 (56)	566 (64)	496 (58)	423 (64)	730 (82)		890
SPE + PPT	796 (64)	719 (58)	545 (58)	846 (68)	732 (59)	436 (66)			1,250
MEPS	351 (54)	324 (49)	479 (73)	353 (54)	298 (45)				656
MeOH 3:1	1201 (70)	1109 (75)	347 (37)	1366 (76)					1,808
MeOH 2:1	1289 (75)	1158 (78)	429 (45)						1,905
HybridSPE	420 (45)	363 (38)							943
ACN 3:1	1287 (87)								1,480
Total	1,725	1,480	943	1,905	1,808	656	1,250	890	

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Table 3 Repeatability of six features with different *m/z* and retention times (*RT*) present in all the replicates of each sample preparation protocol

Feature	<i>m/z</i>	RT (s)	CV							
				ACN 2:1	ACN 3:1	HybridSPE	MeOH 2:1	MeOH 3:1	MEPS	SPE + PPT
M227T46	226.952	45.8	0.06	0.15	0.09	0.11	0.10	0.27	0.04	0.22
M195T406	195.088	405.6	0.15	0.23	0.23	0.20	0.03	0.10	0.21	0.11
M314T587	314.233	587.0	0.11	0.06	0.29	0.16	0.13	0.14	0.08	0.19
M460T652	460.270	652.3	0.21	0.18	0.12	0.22	0.57	0.10	0.18	0.48
M637T772	637.306	772.3	0.27	0.24	0.25	0.18	0.20	0.11	0.15	0.10
M804T862	803.543	862.3	0.05	0.07	0.03	0.09	0.13	0.06	0.06	0.12
Mean CV			0.14	0.15	0.17	0.16	0.19	0.13	0.12	0.20
Mean CV of instrumental replicates			0.11	0.16	0.05	0.18	0.11	0.07	0.04	0.17

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CV coefficient of variation

Table 4 Absorbance measurements and concentrations of residual protein (expressed as mean±confidence interval; 95 % confidence level) estimated for each plasma preparation protocol using the Bradford assay

Bradford assay	ACN 2:1	ACN 3:1	HybridSPE	MeOH 2:1	MeOH 3:1	MEPS	SPE + PPT	SPE
Measure 1	0.625	0.598	0.586	1.619	1.559	0.635	0.680	0.735
Measure 2	0.603	0.599	0.605	1.614	1.49	0.590	0.734	0.777
Measure 3	0.622	0.589	0.596	1.664	1.499	0.622	0.695	0.658
Mean	0.617	0.595	0.596	1.632	1.516	0.635	0.703	0.723
Concentration (mg/L)	2.5±0.4	1.9±0.2	2.0±0.4	26±1	24±2	3±1	4±1	5±3

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